

FACTORS FOR DEVELOPING PRODUCTION AND INCREASING COMPETITIVENESS ON FARM HOLDINGS

Nazarova Gulruh Umarjonovna

Teacher, Karshi Institute of Engineering Economics

E-mail: nazarovagulruh72@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-6188-6844>

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the factors that contribute to the formation of marketing strategies and increase the competitiveness of farms in the agricultural sector. The study examines key aspects such as the development of effective marketing strategies for farms, the use of digital technologies and innovative marketing tools, market segmentation, pricing policy, and branding. The study also highlights practical methods and approaches necessary for the successful sale of farm products in the market and increasing their competitiveness, including issues of environmentally friendly products and quality improvement.

Introduction The need to develop effective marketing strategies for the successful operation of farms in the agricultural sector in the region, primarily to adapt to market requirements and increase their competitiveness, is increasing day by day. Farms are mainly engaged in the production of agricultural products and their marketing. However, today, increased competition, rapid changes in market conditions and diversification of consumer demands create the need for farmers to develop new marketing approaches. To increase the competitiveness of farms, it is important to correctly formulate marketing strategies, successfully market products, use branding and modern marketing tools.

This study uses several methodological approaches to formulate a marketing strategy in farms and identify factors that increase competitiveness. The main goal of the study is to identify the methods and strategies necessary for the effective organization of marketing activities in farms and increasing competitiveness in market conditions. Scientific research on the development of an effective marketing strategy in farms in the conditions of the local market, studies by Uzbek and foreign scientists, shed light on the importance of marketing strategies and how they can be effectively used in the agricultural sector. Below we will analyze the scientific work of Uzbek and foreign scientists in this area.

Drucker, P. As the founder of the concept of innovation and entrepreneurship, Drucker in his work "Innovation and Entrepreneurship" defines innovation as an integral part of entrepreneurial activity. He justifies increasing competitiveness through innovative

approaches within clusters. In farms, these ideas serve as an important theoretical basis for developing marketing strategies. [1] Kotler, F., Keller, K.L. In their work "Marketing Management", they deeply cover the concepts of marketing mix (4P), branding, market positioning and digital marketing. It is shown that it is possible to strengthen the market position for farms through these strategies [2]. Toshpulatov, Sh. analyzed the main directions of marketing strategies in farms and expressed important ideas on how to apply the 4P approach specifically in agriculture. This scientific work is used in the development of strategic approaches adapted to regional characteristics. [3] Rasulov, D., revealing the specifics of marketing in agriculture, emphasizes the need to adapt product promotion and pricing strategies to traditional market conditions. These ideas serve as a basis for improving regional marketing approaches. [4] Mirzayev, B. In his research on developing customized marketing strategies for farmers in Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the use of digital tools, pricing policy, and branding. He especially substantiates the importance of marketing analysis with practical examples. [5] Porter, M. As the founder of cluster theory, Porter's work "Competitive Advantage" explains how farms can integrate themselves into the economic system and strengthen their marketing and competitive strategies through clusters. [6] Soliyev, M., Abdukodirov, A. This article, written by local authors, examines the scientific foundations of developing marketing infrastructure, managing information flows, and studying the market in agroclusters. The article directly corresponds to the topic of the research. [7] Tashkent State University of Economics (2023) Seminar materials on "Digital Transformation and Marketing Approaches in Agriculture" analyze the importance of agrotechnologies, digital marketplaces, and e-platforms for farmers.[8] The analyzed literature shows that the issue of forming marketing strategies and increasing competitiveness in farms has been approached based on various theoretical and practical approaches. While classical thinkers such as Drucker and Porter analyzed marketing strategies in the framework of innovation, clustering, and competitive advantage, Kotler and Keller deeply revealed modern marketing instruments, including the 4P model, branding, and market segmentation.

Uzbek researchers - Toshpulatov, Rasulov, Mirzayev and others - adapted these theories to the conditions of the national economy, especially agriculture. Based on their research, it was determined that it is important to develop marketing approaches adapted to the needs of farms, taking into account territorial, social and technological factors. It was also shown that promoting products through digital technologies, electronic trading platforms and social networks plays an important role in expanding the market and increasing the customer base. This justifies the need for an innovative and integrated approach to developing a marketing strategy. In general, the analysis of the literature shows that for the effective formation of marketing strategies in farms, it is important to combine practical methods suitable for local conditions, along with classical theories.

The introduction of modern marketing techniques in the agricultural sector not only helps to sell products, but also helps to deeply analyze farmers' market needs and consumer demands. In this process, the widespread use of new tools such as digital marketing and online shopping creates opportunities for farmers to successfully introduce their products to a wide audience and sell them. In addition, farmers can add value to their products through

market segmentation, pricing policy, improving product quality, and producing environmentally friendly products.

The increase in product quality, their production without harming ecosystems, is highly appreciated by consumers. As the first stage of the study, the existing scientific literature and research are analyzed. The works of Uzbek and foreign scientists on agricultural marketing, increasing competitiveness, market analysis, and marketing strategies are studied. At this stage, the main attention is paid to the analysis of factors affecting the marketing strategies of farms, modern marketing tools, and market demands.

Questionnaires and interviews: The study will conduct questionnaires and interviews to identify marketing strategies of farms and study practical skills related to increasing competitiveness. Questionnaires will be conducted among farmers, agricultural specialists, and marketing experts. This process will help to identify marketing strategies used by farmers and difficulties in increasing competitiveness in the market. Also, through interviews, detailed information will be obtained about the problems that have arisen in practice and their solutions.

Market analysis: The study will use the main methodological approaches to market analysis. Market segmentation, consumer needs, and competitor activities will be studied. In order for farms to be successful in selling their products, it is necessary to analyze market conditions that will help increase competitiveness. The study will deeply analyze current market conditions, changes in supply and demand, pricing policy, and the importance of branding.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis: The study will use a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative methods are used to study the problems of properly formulating marketing strategies of farms and increasing their competitiveness. Quantitative methods are used to measure the effectiveness of marketing strategies, the economic impact of increasing competitiveness, and the level of success in adapting to changing market conditions. This methodology allows for practical results to be obtained on increasing the effectiveness of marketing strategies and competitiveness. Expert assessment: At the final stages of the study, an expert assessment is conducted by marketing specialists and agricultural experts. The results obtained with the help of experts are analyzed and practical recommendations are developed to form effective marketing strategies and increase competitiveness in the agricultural market.

Development of practical recommendations and strategies: Based on the results of the study, practical recommendations are developed for the formation of marketing strategies and increasing competitiveness in farms. These recommendations will help to overcome the difficulties encountered in implementing marketing strategies and help farmers successfully operate in market conditions. Thus, the study deeply studies the methodological approaches to the formation of marketing strategies and increasing competitiveness in farms, the tools used in practice, and the effectiveness of market analysis. Through the results of the study, farmers are provided with practical recommendations for the correct formation of marketing and increasing competitiveness.

The results of the study show that the effective implementation of marketing strategies plays a major role in increasing the competitiveness of farms. Farmers have realized that in

order to successfully sell their products on the market, marketing should be used not only by advertising products, but also by implementing market segmentation, developing a pricing policy, and studying consumer needs. In addition, innovative approaches to marketing strategies, including the use of digital marketing and online sales platforms, help farmers strengthen their position in the market.

The results of the study showed that effective implementation of marketing strategies allows farmers to quickly adapt to market conditions, reach a wider audience, and increase competitiveness. Market analysis, consumer demand research, and the correct use of marketing tools are essential for farms to capture the market and create demand for their products.

To increase competitiveness, farmers can create added value for their products by introducing branding and digital technologies, as well as improving market segmentation and optimizing pricing policies. The main directions indicated in the study include important methodologies that should be used when formulating marketing strategies for farmers.

Strengthen market segmentation and analysis: Farmers need to reach their target audience through proper market segmentation. It is necessary to develop appropriate marketing strategies for each market segment, analyze consumer needs, and create products based on their requirements.

Develop digital marketing and online sales: Wider use of digital marketing and online sales platforms can be an important strategic tool for farmers. Further expanding online sales opportunities, conducting marketing activities through social networks and websites will help expand the market. Also, effective advertising and product information dissemination through digital marketing will allow you to get closer to consumers.

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